

Synthesis and antibacterial activity of new *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas

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A new series of *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas have been prepared in excellent yield by the reaction of acylthiocyanates and 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline under solid-liquid phase transfer catalysis using PEG-400. All synthesised compounds were screened against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in DMF for evaluating their antibacterial activity. 2d, 2e, 2f and 2g showed good activity at 50 µg/ml dilution.

N,N'-Disubstituted thioureas are well known as potassium channel openers in the treatment of cardio-vascular disorders, potential plant growth regulators and good antibacterials¹. The 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline moiety has been incorporated in the title compounds since this moiety has been reported as a pharmacophore of many aromatic and heterocyclic compounds which exhibited antitubercular, antimicrobial and tyrosinekinase inhibitory activity². So it was contemplated to synthesise new *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas (2a-g) and screened them for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Results and discussion

We adopted the method³ for the synthesis of title com-

pounds by the reaction of an appropriate acid chloride and ammonium thiocyanate under solid-liquid phase transfer catalysis using PEG-400 in methylene chloride as solvent at room temperature followed by stirring with 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline (Scheme 1). The highlight of the synthesis is short time of one and half hour giving excellent yields. Structures of the final product were confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data (Tables 1 and 2). All seven compounds 2a-g were screened against human pathogenic bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Compounds 2a-g were tested for antibacterial activity using two strains *Escherichia coli* (NCTC 10418) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (NCTC 5571) at 100 µg/ml and 50 µg/ml dilution in DMF following the cup plate method⁴.

Table I. Preparation of *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Needles	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.) %		
						C	H	N
2a	CH ₃	60	135-136	Pale yellow	C ₉ H ₈ ClFN ₂ OS (43.81)	43.70 (43.81)	3.37 (3.24)	11.12 (11.24)
2b	Ph	91	141-142	Colourless	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ OS (54.45)	54.68 (54.45)	3.46 (3.24)	8.93 (9.10)
2c	<i>p</i> -ClPh	92	184-185	Colourless	C ₁₄ H ₉ Cl ₂ FN ₂ OS (49.92)	50.05 (49.92)	2.75 (2.64)	8.24 (8.19)
2d	<i>p</i> -Cl ₂ Ph	88	123-124	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ OS (55.80)	56.06 (55.80)	3.58 (3.72)	8.80 (8.68)
2e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	90	184-185	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClFN ₃ O ₃ S (47.52)	47.77 (47.52)	2.75 (2.54)	11.77 (11.80)
2f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	88	168-170	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S (53.17)	53.55 (53.17)	3.35 (3.54)	8.45 (8.27)
2g	3-Pyridyl	90	179-181	Pale yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClFN ₃ OS (50.40)	50.31 (50.40)	3.11 (2.90)	13.38 (13.57)

Table 2. UV, IR and ¹H NMR data of *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas

Compd.	λ nm (ε)	IR (γ _{max} cm ⁻¹)			¹ H NMR (DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆)			
		NH (br)	C=O (s)	C=S (m)	ArH	NH	N'H	CH ₃
2a	276 (26, 231)	3187	1689	1170	7.55–7.00 (3H, m)	12.24 (1H, s)	9.00 (1H, s)	2.00 (s, COCH ₃)
2b	280 (35, 714)	3235	1672	1159	8.12–7.06 (8H, m)	12.24 (1H, s)	9.05 (1H, s)	
2c	287 (34, 843)	3194	1660	1158	7.95–7.31 (7H, m)	12.00 (1H, s)	9.11 (1H, s)	
2d	282 (35, 460)	3215	1684	1172	7.90–7.28 (7H, m)	12.20 (1H, s)	9.10 (1H, s)	2.24 (s, CH ₃)
2e	288 (34, 722)	3280	1680	1163	8.12–7.18 (7H, m)	12.15 (1H, s)	9.42 (1H, s)	
2f	284 (35, 211)	3299	1655	1158	7.85–7.30 (7H, m)	12.28 (1H, s)	9.25 (1H, s)	3.80 (s, OCH ₃)
2g	271 (36, 900)	3250	1672	1149	8.10–7.12 (7H, m)	12.20 (1H, s)	9.00 (1H, s)	

Norfloxacin and sulfamethoxazole were used as reference drugs for comparison of the activities. The results are presented as in Table 3. The results indicated that **2d**, **2e** and **2f** having *p*-methyl, *p*-nitro and *p*-methoxyphenyl substitution contributed to greater activity even at 50 μg/ml dilution. Also **2g** having 3-pyridyl substitution showed good activity.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas

Compd.	R	<i>E. coli</i> (μm/ml)		<i>S. aureus</i> (μm/ml)	
		100	50	100	50
2a	CH ₃	17	11	15	13
2b	Ph	15	12	15	12
2c	<i>p</i> -ClPh	18	16	21	17
2d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ Ph	28	22	26	20
2e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	20	20	20	18
2f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	21	20	24	21
2g	3-Pyridyl	24	20	22	19
Norfloxacin		>30	>30	>30	>30
Sulphamethoxazole		28	28	24	24

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. 3-Chloro-4-fluoroaniline was purchased from Lancaster, London, UK. The phase transfer catalyst PEG-400, acetylchloride, benzoylchloride, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-methoxybenzoic acid and nicotinic acid were purchased from s.d. Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Nicolet FT-IR 410 spectrometer (wave numbers as cm⁻¹) and ¹H NMR in DMSO-*d*₆ on Varian RX-300 MHz FT spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard (chemical shifts in δ). UV spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 2000 UV-Visi-

where, R = a, CH₃; b, Ph; c, *p*-ClPh; d, *p*-CH₃Ph; e, *p*-NO₂Ph; f, *p*-OCH₃Ph; g, 3-pyridyl

Scheme 1

ble spectrophotometer (λ_{max} as nm (ε) in methanol). C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Thermoquest CHN analyzer. These data were obtained from the instruments at University Scientific Instruments Centre, Karnatak University, Dharwad.

Preparation of acyl chlorides (1a-g) :

p-Chlorobenzoyl chloride (b.p. 222–224°C), *p*-methylbenzoyl chloride (b.p. 225–227°C), *p*-methoxybenzoyl chloride (b.p. 208–210°C), nicotinyl chloride (b.p. 110–115°C/25 mm) and *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (m.p. 71–73°C) were prepared according to the literature methods⁵.

General procedure for the preparation of *N*-acyl-*N'*-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)thioureas (2a-g) :

A mixture of powdered ammonium thiocyanate (0.02 mol), acyl chloride (0.01 mol), PEG-400 (3% with respect to ammonium thiocyanate) and methylene chloride (45 ml) was stirred well at room temperature for 1 h. Then 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was further stirred for 30 min. The inorganic salts were removed

Note

by filtration and washed with methylene chloride (10 ml). Filtrates were combined and solvent removed on a rotary evaporator under diminished pressure to obtain solid product. Each product was recrystallised from ethanol and their physicochemical data were determined (Tables 1 and 2).

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